

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 18th February 2022
Accepted: 23th February 2022
Online: 27th February 2022

KEY WORDS

Republic of Uzbekistan, state customs service, law, administrative-legal status, rights and obligations, customs officers.

Service in customs bodies and organizations is a public service based on a special regime, organized under the jurisdiction of the Republic of Uzbekistan and financed from the state budget. Its legal regulation is carried out only at the republican level and is based on the Constitution, laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as normative legal acts of the President and the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan. However, the procedure for determining the legal status of customs officers is carried out within the competent authorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan, established by the legislation. In particular, the customs authorities are established and abolished by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Regulations on the State Customs Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall be approved by

ADMINISTRATIVE AND LEGAL STATUS OF CUSTOMS OFFICERS

Khosiyatkhon Abdurakhmonova

DSc, Docent, Acting Professor, Department of Public Law,
Customs Institute of the State Customs
Committee of the Republic Of Uzbekistan

E-mail: xosiyat.1986@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6344230>

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the administrative and legal status of customs officials in the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and developed foreign countries. The main tasks and responsibilities of the State Customs Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the customs authorities are analyzed.

the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Customs bodies shall be headed by the Chairman of the State Customs Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Chairman of the State Customs Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan has the authority, if necessary, to make changes in the organizational and staffing structures of the customs authorities within the established total number of staff. Customs points may be established within customs posts. Customs points are established and liquidated by the Chairman of the State Customs Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Public service - activities to fulfill the request of citizens or organizations for the recognition, establishment, change or termination of their rights, the establishment of legal facts, the receipt for

their implementation in cases and in the manner prescribed by law, material and financial resources, as well as the provision of documented information on issues, included in accordance with this republic law in the register of public services.

At the same time, a request for the provision of a public service is a demand of citizens or organizations for the provision of a public service, expressed orally, in writing or electronically and submitted to the body providing the public service [2].

In this regard, the term "State Customs Service" should be conditionally differentiated and interpreted in a broad and narrow sense. "Customs Service" in the broadest sense is the State Customs Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, departments of the State Customs Committee of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions, Tashkent city, "Tashkent-AERO" specialized customs complex, customs posts, Customs Institute of the State Customs Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the National Cynology Center organs.

"Customs service" in the narrow sense is a type of public service, which is the executive branch. This means that it implements a unified state policy in the field of providing public services to individuals and legal entities.

Thus, the customs authorities are established to implement a single customs policy and protect the economic interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan. At the same time, the customs authorities are law enforcement agencies. The main principles of the customs authorities are legality, unity, openness and transparency, observance of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of individuals and legal

entities, as well as respect for these rights, freedoms and legitimate interests.

In the field of customs services, there are three main segments that include:

1) state customs services provided as part of the customs administration process;

2) services accompanying the process of customs clearance, provided by the customs authorities and paid by participants in foreign economic activity in the form of customs fees;

3) customs services of a commercial nature, provided by entities near the customs service market.

The customs authorities have the following rights in carrying out the tasks assigned to them. In particular, the exercise of rights such as verification of information and documents for customs control, request and receipt of information and documents related to customs control, export-import operations, pre-investigation inspection, inquiry and operational search activities increases.

In our opinion, the issues of ensuring compliance with the law in the framework of foreign trade activities in relation to the object moving from the territory of one state to the territory of another state are the basis for the prevention of a number of national and international crimes.

According to Wieslaw "Wes" CZYŻOWICZ, Ewa GWARDZIŃSKA, the application of the principle of legality in the field of customs is welcomed. Among the EU Member States, only Spain, Greece, Italy, France, Malta, Cyprus, Lithuania, Latvia, Poland and Portugal have the issue of customs representation regulated by the law. As confirmed by statistics, these states have a relatively low number of customs frauds and irregularities, as compared to

the states which have not regulated the issue in their legal systems [3].

According to the customs law of the People's Republic of China, the Customs of the People's Republic of China is a governmental organization responsible for supervision and control over all arrivals in and departures from the Customs territory. It shall, in accordance with this Law and other related laws and administrative regulations, exercise control over means of transport, goods, travellers' luggage, postal items and other articles entering or leaving the territory (hereinafter referred to as inward and outward means of transport, goods and articles), collect Customs duties and other taxes and fees, prevent and combat smuggling, compile Customs statistics and handle other Customs operations. The State Council sets up the Customs General Administration, which is charged with the responsibility of carrying unified administration of all the Customs offices throughout the country. Customs offices are set up by the State at ports of entry open to foreign trade and at places and regions that require concentrated Customs operations. The subordination of one Customs office to another shall not be restricted by administrative divisions. The Customs offices exercise their functions and powers independently in accordance with the law and are accountable to the Customs General Administration [4].

The state customs authorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall exercise control over the observance of the customs legislation, control over the correct calculation, full and timely payment of customs duties; organization of customs control; timely notification of individuals and legal entities of their rights and obligations during the movement of goods

and means of transport, as well as crossing the customs border of the Republic of Uzbekistan; not to disclose information constituting state secrets or other secrets protected by law, which became known to him in the performance of his official duties; take measures to prevent violations, identify and eliminate the causes and conditions that led to their occurrence; take measures to prevent corruption and other official crimes in the customs authorities; to assist in the implementation of measures to protect state security, public order, life and health of citizens, and the environment; conditional obligations to ensure compliance with information security requirements in the use of information and communication technologies.

A citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan serving in the customs authorities, who has been awarded a special title, is an employee of the customs authority. Samples of uniforms for customs officials shall be approved by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. A customs officer will be issued a service certificate and a personal digital token. A customs officer may not be a member of a political party during the period of service. Social protection of customs officers is provided by:

- health care;
- remuneration of labor;
- provision of housing space;
- compensation for damage to property;
- state pension provision;
- state insurance;
- social assistance.

The legislation may also provide for other measures for the social protection of customs officials [1].

Based on the above analysis, such a conclusion can be made.

First, the concept of the state customs service, in its broadest and narrowest sense, is a body that performs the internal and external functions of the state.

Second, each country has its own legal system and legislation in the field of customs.

Third, the rights and obligations of customs officers must be exercised in accordance with the law.

REFERENCES:

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Customs Service", No. ZRU-502 of 18.10.2018. <https://lex.uz/docs/4000640>.
2. Boikova M.V. Foreign experience of customs administration / M.V. Boikov; under total ed. V.V. Makrusev. M.: RIO of the Russian Customs Academy, 2017. 130 p. http://rta.customs.ru/nrta/attachments/3756_978-5-9590-0935-9.pdf.
3. Customs representation in Poland. Wieslaw „Wes” CZYŻOWICZ, Ewa GWARDZIŃSKA. coomd.org/-/media/wco/public/global/pdf/topics/capacity-building/resources/scientific-journal/scientific-journal_1_2012.pdf.
4. General Administration of Customs of the People's Republic of China. Jianguomennei Avenue, Dongcheng District, Beijing, China. Postcode: 100730. <http://english.customs.gov.cn/>